

Information in Newtonian Mechanics, Classical Statistical Mechanics and Special Relativity

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Newtonian mechanics is deterministic which we suggest may be thought of in terms of information. If one has a particle at rest at t , $x_0=0$, with $KE=0$, $p=0$ (momentum) then an impulse hit changes $KE=p^2/2m$ $p=0$ to p and $x=vt$. In other words, one initially knows the set (x,t,KE,p) before a force is applied and has the same set (x,t, KE, p) afterwards. We argue that there is no gain or loss in the amount of information during this interaction.

Next, we try to apply this same idea to an ideal gas in a box. We define an ideal gas such that one has minimum information. In other words, for a box of size V , each particle can be at any space point with the same probability. Furthermore, for elastic collisions $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, we use $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ so there is no bias. This leads to $f(e_i) = C \exp(-ie_i/T)$ and $E_{ave} = 3/2 nRT$. One may directly calculate pressure or use the ideal gas law $PV=nRT$. We argue that if one has box of such a case and acts on one wall with a force to change the volume by dV (i.e. dx for a rectangular box with F against one wall), then this is no different than F acting on the particles near or at the wall, i.e. within dx and a few others that move in during the tiny dt . If there is no gain in information when F acts on a single particle, as argued in the first paragraph, then there should be no gain for a collection of such particles.

We start with $dE_{ave} = -PdV$. We define information as a function $F(V,T)$ and argue that $F(V,T) = F(V+dV, T+dT)$. This is identical to stating that $\ln(F(V,T)) = \ln(F(T+dT, V+dV))$. We introduce \ln because it makes the mathematics simpler as will be seen. We define information for a gas particle using its position and energy. This is not the full set used for the single particle, but we argue that it is the relevant information. Then, this information should not change for both F acting on a single particle and acting on the box. We define this \ln information as being proportional to: $\ln V + \ln (N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!)$. If one suggests that $n(e_i)$ is very large, then $\ln(n)$ approx = $n \ln$. Finally, we assume that one has no bias in the box which yields $f(e_i) = C \exp(-ie_i/T)$ as noted above. These ideas then lead to a \ln information whose first order change in T and V is 0. In other words, both the single particle classical case of Force acting on a single particle and the case of Force acting on a wall, i.e. many particles, do not increase the amount of information.

We then extend this notion to special relativity. At first glance, one might consider this to follow the same constant information as the situation in which a force acts on a single particle. In special relativity, however, one has extra information in the way of Lorentz invariants. Thus, it is true that for a particle at rest one has $E=mc^2$, x_0 , t and $p=0$ and for a moving one E',x',t',p' , but one also has the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$. This leads to an issue, because there are different x',t' values which yield the same A . From the point of view of A as information, one has $A = -t mc^2$ in the rest frame, but $x'=x'_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p'$ and $t'=t'_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E'$ (1D) in the moving frame. This suggests a different information scheme, namely one linked with free particle quantum mechanics.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian or classical mechanics (nonrelativistic) is deterministic which means that there is no uncertainty, i.e. there is complete information about a particle. What specifically is this information?

Rest mass m_0 , t , x , $p = mv$, $v(x)$ and $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)v(x)$ and potential energy if there is a potential ((1))

In principle, one needs $x(t)$ which yields $v(t)$ and one may obtain the rest of the information from this.

We argue that if one has a particle at rest and one acts on it to give it a constant velocity, the amount of information does not change, i.e. is constant. In other words, one knows $x=vt + x_0$ where x_0 is the x position at $t=0$. We suggest that this idea may be applied to a scenario in which one does not know all of the information about particles, namely an ideal gas. The information one knows is probabilistic and based on the probability for a particle to be a certain x point and have a kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2}mv^2 = \frac{p^2}{2m}$. This is equivalent to having the probabilities for the two key pieces of information: position and magnitude of velocity.

A main point we wish to make is that if one pushes against a wall of the container which is movable, then the wall imparts force on the particles that strike it in a Newtonian manner which preserves the amount of information present. Thus, at the beginning one knows E_{ave} , T (temperature), N the number of particles and V (volume). We will argue that for an ideal gas, $E_{ave}(T)$ and so for a fixed N , changing the position of one wall changes T to $T+dT$ and V to $V+dV$. The information before and after must be the same.

The Ideal Gas Case

It is well-known that an ideal gas satisfies $PV=nRT$ and $E=\frac{3}{2} n RT$ (3D). These values may be obtained from a probabilistic treatment of the gas which assumes minimum information about collisions i.e.

Collisions are assumed to be elastic so $e_1+e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((2))

The probability for any $e_i + e_j$ collision is $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ and if $e_i+e_j=E$ this product of probabilities is the same to minimize information.

This leads to: $f(e_i) = C \exp(-ie_i/t)$ and $PV=nRT$ and $E=\frac{3}{2}nRT$. ((3)) Here we assume that the particle can be any point in V with the same probability. ((3)) are standard results which are derived in many places. $PV=nRT$ was first obtained experimentally.

Our goal is to use the results of ((3)) together with the idea that overall information cannot change when a wall is pushed from x to $x+dx$ with nothing else happening (i.e. no heat entering or leaving). We only consider a change of dx and so equilibrium exists before and then occurs after in this adiabatic scenario. At this point, we suggest that there is no notion of entropy.

No Change in Information

If Force(x) acting on a point particle does not change its information, we suggest that moving a wall of an ideal gas also does not change information overall because the force acts on a set of particles. It seems, however, that both T and V change. V clearly changes and T represents the amount of energy which changes because work is done on the few particles striking the wall as $x \rightarrow x+dx$. Thus:

$$dE_{\text{average}} = -PdV \quad \text{where } PV=nRT \quad ((3))$$

The question is now to determine an expression for information $G(V,T)$ such that:

$$G(V,T) = G(V+dV, T+dT) \quad ((4))$$

We suggest that V and T are separable and that $1/V$ is the probability for the particle to be any point in V. One may take \ln of both sides of ((4)). We do this as a mathematical convenience which will be shown in the next few steps.

$$\ln\{G(V,T)\} = \ln\{G(V+dV, T+dT)\} \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{So: } 0 = dV/V + dT/dT \ln Q(T) \quad ((5))$$

Here $Q(T)$ describes the information about energies of particles. We suggest that:

$$Q = N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)! \quad \text{Where } e_i \text{ is a single particle kinetic energy and } n(e_i) \text{ the number of particles with this energy} \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Thus, one wishes to take the } d/dT \text{ derivative of } \sum \text{ over } i \ n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \quad ((7))$$

We note that an ideal gas is a special situation, namely one which minimizes bias. Thus, one wishes to have the maximum number of states Q subject to the constraint: $\sum \text{ over } i \ n(e_i) e_i = E_{\text{ave}}$, where E_{ave} is a fixed number.

$$\text{Thus: } \delta \left(\sum \text{ over } i \ n \ln(n) - B \sum \text{ over } i \ e_i n(e_i) \right) = 0 \quad ((8))$$

This leads to $n(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ if $B=1/T$. $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ was already obtained above using a different approach.

$$\text{Now taking } d/dT \text{ is proportional to } \delta \text{ acting on } n(e_i). \quad \text{Thus, } dQ/dT = 1/T \ d/dT E_{\text{ave}} \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{Thus, ((5)) becomes: } 0 = dV/V + dT/T \ 3/2 \ nR \quad ((10))$$

If one uses $dE_{ave} = -PdV$ one has: $\frac{3}{2} nR dT = nRT/V dV$ so $dV/V = \frac{3}{2} dT/T$ ((11)) rendering ((10)) equal to 0 as required.

Thus, a force which changes V to $V+dV$ with no heat coming in or out does not change information. We note at this point we have no sense of a formal entropy or the first law of thermodynamics. We have only considered a force acting on a single particle not changing the amount of information and extended this to a special gas, namely an ideal gas. This leads to the definition of the \ln of something we call information which remains constant. One may, however, that this \ln information is actually proportional to entropy used in classical statistical mechanics.

The Case of Special Relativity

In the above sections which considered the nonrelativistic case. One might at first think that information remains constant also in the special relativistic case of a force acting on a single particle. The particle has an x,t, p,E and after the force acts, a new x',t', p',E' . This appears to be analogous to the nonrelativistic case except for one issue. In special relativity there are Lorentz invariants which do not appear in nonrelativistic theory explicitly. They are actually present there too as we will show, but first we consider the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et+px \quad ((12))$$

A has the same value when one transforms the two vectors (x,t) and (p,E) to (x',t') and (p',E') . The problem is that for a fixed p',E' there are alternative x' and t' values which keep A constant, namely:

$$x=x_0 + n\hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t=t_0 + n\hbar/E \quad \text{where } n \text{ is an integer} \quad ((13))$$

One may choose to ignore this and remain with a classical viewpoint or accept it and ultimately obtain a free particle quantum mechanical picture. What one sees is that both spatial and time have extra information given by \hbar/p and \hbar/E . If these are treated as resolutions, then a particle with \hbar/p resolution can be in Lp/\hbar positions in a length L , while one with p_2 , in Lp_2/\hbar . If $p_2 > p_1$, there are more positions for p_2 , hence more information according to the classical recipe dV/V given in previous sections. In such a case, doing work on a free particle relativistically changes information about space and time and so is associated with a completely different viewpoint.

One may ask: What happens nonrelativistically? In such a case: $p \rightarrow mv$ and $E \rightarrow m_0c^2 + pp/2m$. One may again have resolution units of \hbar/p for x and \hbar/KE which leave A the same as for a given x_0, t_0 . Thus, the resolution picture remains even in the nonrelativistic limit. (One may also not both relativistically and nonrelativistically $-Et+px$ is the class action. For the nonrelativistic case $E = pp/2m$.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a force acting on a nonrelativistic particle changes its velocity, but not the amount of information one has about the particle. Before the hit, the particle had an m_0 , x , t , $p = mv$ and $KE = p^2/m_0$. After, it also has this same set of variables so new information is created.

We suggest that if one considers an ideal gas in a box and moves one wall by dx using a force, then this is equivalent to acting on a few particles near this wall and so overall no information should change.

An ideal gas is not described by following each particle's set of x, t, m_0, p, KE , but rather probabilistically through V and $n(e_i)$, the number of particles with kinetic energy e_i . One may find that $n(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ without any concept of entropy by using $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$. If there is no bias, then any $e_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2$ is as good as another. This leads to $E_{ave} = 3/2 nRT$ and $PV = nRT$.

For the case of moving a wall, we suggest $dE = PdV$ if no heat leaves or enters the gas. We suggest that overall information cannot change. We define information as proportional to $V G_1(T)$ and argue that $\ln(V G_1(T)) = \ln((V+dV) G_1(T+dT))$. Next, we use $G_1 = N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!$ Together with Stirling's approximation $n! \approx n \ln n$. This approach shows that information does not change in this example, where we use $\ln(\text{information})$ as our function. At this point there is no concept of entropy or of a first law of thermodynamics.

We then consider the case of special relativity and argue that a given the presence of the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$, a force leads to resolution units of \hbar/p and \hbar/E (space and time) and these affects spatial and temporal knowledge unlike the nonrelativistic case.